

PLANAR SCARF JOINTS IN COMPOSITE REPAIR*

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This study examined the effects of varying certain important geometric parameters on the stresses in an adhesive repair of a thin composite laminate. The repair, a planar scarf joint with a doubler, was studied using finite element methods at scarf angles of 6° and 12° , damage lengths between 2.5 mm and 25 mm and doubler overlaps between 10 mm and 40 mm. Finite element models also showed that significant stress peaks occur at the ends of the scarf joint adhesive, similar to shear lag phenomena in lap joints. A bending model of the planar scarf joint with a doubler, based on mechanics of materials theory, was also developed.

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Introduction

The increasing use of composite materials in practical applications makes relatively simple and effective repair methods very desirable. We chose to study the repair of a laminate accessible from only one side using only machining which could be done in place. The repair was studied by linear elastic finite element methods. It includes the composite laminate, with the damaged part removed and the edges tapered. A mating piece which replaces the removed laminate is adhesively bonded to the remaining laminate. The scarf joint may be covered with an adhesively bonded doubler.

The parameters studied were:

- scarf angle, α , or inclination of the joint
- damage length, d , the length of composite removed
- doubler overlap, ℓ , the distance the doubler extends beyond the scarf joint

Finite element studies of the planar scarf joint repair provide background for further work on both analytical modeling of the repair and studies of three-dimensional scarf inclusion repairs.

Finite Element Analysis

The planar scarf joint chosen for the finite element model was a tensile specimen 300 mm long by 38 mm wide as shown in Figure 1. The composite laminate is 2.5 mm in thickness, while the adhesive layers and doubler are 0.25 mm in thickness. The composite is an 18 ply $[0_2/\pm 45/90/\pm 45/0_2]_S$ graphite-epoxy laminate (Hercules AS/3501) which is treated as an orthotropic material in the finite element analysis.

Fig. 1 - Planar scarf joint with doubler (side view).

Stress Analysis Program IV (SAP IV) was employed in the finite element studies of the planar scarf joint. The two dimensional quadrilateral element, which accommodates orthotropic material properties, was used in the mesh shown in Figure 2. With this mesh, scarf angle, damage length and doubler overlap, can be varied by changing only y-coordinates of the nodes. This is relatively straight forward using the mesh generation program of SAP IV. The plane stress option was used throughout.

Fig. 2 - Finite element mesh.

Effective material properties for the laminate were calculated using classical thin lamination theory. Properties in the thickness (z) direction were calculated assuming that $E_3 = E_2$, $\nu_{13} = \nu_{12}$ and $\nu_{23} = \nu_{\text{matrix}}$. Assumed lamina properties are

$$E_1 = 137 \text{ GPa } (19.9 \times 10^6 \text{ psi})$$

$$E_2 = 9.65 \text{ GPa } (1.4 \times 10^6 \text{ psi})$$

$$\nu_{12} = 0.27$$

$$\nu_{\text{matrix}} = 0.40$$

$$G_{12} = 4.40 \text{ GPa } (640. \text{ ksi}).$$

The orthotropic material constants of the 18 ply laminate are then

$$E_x = 35.4 \text{ GPa } (5.13 \times 10^6 \text{ psi})$$

$$E_y = 74.5 \text{ GPa } (10.8 \times 10^6 \text{ psi})$$

$$E_z = 9.65 \text{ GPa } (1.4 \times 10^6 \text{ psi})$$

$$\nu_{yz} = 0.028$$

$$\nu_{xy} = 0.20$$

$$\nu_{xz} = 0.32$$

$$G_{yz} = 4.14 \text{ GPa } (0.6 \times 10^6 \text{ psi})$$

Where the xyz coordinate system is shown in Figure 2.

For the two ply $[0/90]$ composite doubler the laminate was treated as symmetric, i.e. bending-extension coupling properties of the doubler were ignored. Properties of the doubler are:

$$E_x = 73.8 \text{ GPa } (10.7 \times 10^6 \text{ psi})$$

$$E_y = 73.8 \text{ GPa } (10.7 \times 10^6 \text{ psi})$$

$$E_z = 17.2 \text{ GPa } (2.49 \times 10^6 \text{ psi})$$

$$\nu_{yz} = 0.050$$

$$\nu_{xy} = 0.035$$

$$\nu_{xz} = 0.384$$

$$G_{yz} = 4.14 \text{ GPa } (0.6 \times 10^6 \text{ psi}).$$

The flexural modulus and the effective elastic modulus of the composite laminate are not the same. However only one can be used in the finite element analysis. The elastic modulus was used here because tensile behavior is of more importance in this problem than flexural behavior.

Specimen Bending

The scarf joint bends under tension because the neutral surface in some regions is not coincident with the applied force. This eccentricity is caused by the added thickness of the doubler and the lower stiffness of the adhesive layer. The bending of the laminate produces two effects. First, curvature at the end of the specimen requires an applied moment. This condition is very difficult to satisfy for any experimental specimen used to verify the analysis. The best solution to this problem is to employ a specimen whose length is great enough that its curvature at the ends, and hence the required moment, is negligible. Analysis of a solid composite specimen, for which a closed form solution is available, shows that a 300 mm specimen has a very small curvature at the end.

The second effect of specimen bending is that the finite element model does not account for changes in bending moment as the specimen deflects. Specimen deflection moves the neutral surface, changing the moment distribution of the specimen due to the eccentric axial force. Because the moment at most sections decreases with deflection the finite element model yields excessively large (and incorrect) deflections. This may be corrected by imposing concentrated couples along the bottom surface of the finite element model. However, this modification requires knowledge of the moment distribution of the loaded specimen.

The moment distribution for a specimen with joint adhesive layers may be calculated from beam theory. All parts of the specimen must satisfy the beam deflection equation:

$$\frac{d^2z}{dy^2} = \frac{P(z+e)}{EI} \quad (1)$$

And the effective section modulus may be calculated at any location from the relation

$$EI = \sum_{n=1}^N E_n I_n \quad (2)$$

which accounts for the lower stiffness of the adhesive layer and the associated change in the location of the neutral surface. Linear distribution of axial strain through the section is assumed in the above.

Equation (1) may be solved by numerical integration, iterating the boundary condition (i.e. midspan deflection) until the end deflection is zero. When the deflection at a section is known the moment distribution for the finite element model can be calculated.

Parametric Study

The effects of changing scarf angle, doubler overlap and damage length

on adhesive stresses were investigated for the 18 ply graphite-epoxy laminate repaired with identical material using an epoxy adhesive and a two ply, [0/90], graphite-epoxy doubler. A tensile load of 7000 N or 73.7 MPa (10,700 psi) was used for all cases.

The maximum shear stress in the scarf adhesive layer of the repair with 6° scarf angle, 25 mm damage length and no doubler is shown in Figure 3. Tensile stress maxima are located at or very near the shear stress maxima. The high stresses at the ends of the adhesive layer are typical of shear lag phenomena observed in lap joints (1). Since the adherends are identical here there is no increase in shear stress at the joint ends due to stiffness mismatch of the adherends. Shear stress would be even higher at the end of the less stiff adherend for dissimilar adherends (2, 3).

Fig. 3 - Maximum shear stress in scarf adhesive layer.

The maximum shear stress in the scarf and doubler adhesive layers of a repair with 6° scarf angle, 25 mm damage length and 25 mm doubler overlap is shown in Figure 4. Shear stress maxima occur at the lower end of the scarf adhesive layer and the end of the doubler adhesive layer. In all cases the tensile stress maxima are located at or very near the shear stress maxima. Stress is greater at the bottom of the adhesive layer compared to the joint with no doubler due to the added eccentricity of the doubler. The stress at the top of the adhesive layer is lower because the doubler covering the end of the adhesive layer reduces the shear lag effect. Stress at the end of the doubler increases very rapidly, similar to a simple lap joint. High stress here is due to stiffness differences between the doubler and the laminate substrate.

Fig. 4 - Maximum shear stress in joint and doubler adhesives of a composite-epoxy scarf joint.

Tensile stress maxima in the y-direction occur at the tapered edges of the replacement material and original laminate and in the doubler directly over the tip of the replacement material. Shear stress and z-direction tensile stress are very small throughout the adherends. However, the finite element mesh in the original laminate under the doubler end was coarse so stress gradients could not be detected and high stresses which cause delamination of the composite might not be detected (4).

Tensile and shear stress maxima in the adhesive layer and tensile stress maxima in the laminates are tabulated in Table I for $\alpha = 6^\circ$ and in Table II for $\alpha = 12^\circ$.

Ultimate repair strength can be predicted by applying any of several strength criteria to the data generated by the finite element analysis. Because adherend stresses are all well below the corresponding laminate ultimate stresses, failure is assumed to occur in the adhesive. For the isotropic adhesive, strength predictions can be made using maximum tensile stress, maximum shear stress, or maximum distortional energy. Maximum tensile stress and maximum shear stress will be considered here. Local ultimate stresses must be known, rather than the average failure stress which is commonly

TABLE I

Tensile and Shear Stress Maxima in the Adhesives and Tensile Stress
Maxima in the Composite Laminates of a Planar Scarf Joint
 $\alpha = 6^\circ$

d	l	scarf adhesive		doubler adhesive		replace-	original	doubler
		σ	τ	σ	τ	ment	composite	
mm	mm	MPa	MPa	MPa	MPa	piece	σ	σ
(in)	(in)	(psi)	(psi)	(psi)	(psi)		(psi)	(psi)
2.5 (0.098)	10 (0.39)	12.0 (1740)	9.05 (1310)	14.7 (2130)	7.68 (1110)	85.3 (12350)	105 (15200)	83.2 (12050)
2.5 (0.098)	40 (1.6)	11.5 (1660)	8.66 (1250)	13.6 (1970)	7.27 (1050)	90.3 (13100)	100 (14500)	90.2 (13100)
15 (0.59)	10 (0.39)	12.1 (1750)	9.14 (1320)	14.5 (2100)	7.56 (1090)	85.7 (12400)	106 (15400)	83.7 (12100)
15 (0.59)	40 (1.6)	11.6 (1680)	8.76 (1270)	13.5 (1960)	7.20 (1040)	90.0 (13000)	101 (14600)	89.6 (13000)
25 (0.98)	10 (1.6)	12.1 (1750)	9.15 (1330)	14.5 (2100)	7.56 (1090)	85.7 (12410)	106 (15400)	83.7 (12100)
25 (0.98)	25 (0.98)	11.7 (1690)	8.78 (1270)	13.6 (1970)	7.33 (1060)	88.8 (12900)	102 (14800)	88.0 (12700)
25 (0.98)	40 (1.6)	11.7 (1690)	8.81 (1280)	13.5 (1960)	7.20 (1040)	90.5 (13100)	102 (14800)	90.4 (13100)
25 (0.98)	no doubler	13.2 (1910)	9.68 (1400)					

TABLE II

Tensile and Shear Stress Maxima in the Adhesives and Tensile Stress Maxima
in the Composite Laminate of a Planar Scarf Joint
 $\alpha = 12^\circ$

d mm (in)	l mm (in)	scarf adhesive		doubler adhesive		replace- ment piece	original composite	doubler
		σ MPa (psi)	τ MPa (psi)	σ MPa (psi)	τ MPa (psi)	σ MPa (psi)	σ MPa (psi)	σ MPa (psi)
2.5 (0.098)	10 (0.39)	28.1 (4070)	19.0 (2750)	11.4 (1650)	6.01 (870)	82.0 (11900)	124 (18000)	84.1 (12200)
2.5 (0.098)	40 (1.6)	25.4 (3680)	17.3 (2510)	11.2 (1620)	6.06 (878)	87.4 (12700)	113 (16400)	97.6 (14100)
15 (0.59)	10 (0.39)	26.4 (3820)	18.0 (2610)	12.4 (1800)	6.53 (946)	83.6 (12100)	117 (16900)	90.9 (13200)
15 (0.59)	40 (1.6)	24.5 (3550)	16.8 (2430)	11.7 (1690)	6.35 (920)	89.7 (13000)	109 (15800)	101 (14600)
25 (0.98)	10 (0.39)	25.8 (3740)	17.6 (2550)	13.0 (1880)	6.85 (992)	86.1 (12500)	115 (16700)	95.1 (13800)
25 (0.98)	25 (0.98)	24.7 (3580)	16.8 (2430)	12.3 (1780)	6.61 (957)	88.7 (12800)	110 (15900)	99.4 (14400)
25 (0.98)	40 (1.6)	24.2 (3510)	16.6 (2400)	12.1 (1750)	6.53 (946)	90.4 (13100)	108 (15600)	103 (14900)
25 (0.98)	no doubler	24.0 (3480)	18.2 (2640)					

reported. Once the failure site is found for a particular repair the ultimate joint strength can be predicted since the local stress is proportional to the load. The predicted ultimate load will be conservative because of adhesive inelasticity. In an actual joint the adhesive will deform inelastically and the stress distribution in the joint at failure may be very different from the distribution predicted by linear elastic theory.

From Tables I and II the scarf adhesive tensile and shear stresses are shown to

- increase with increases in the scarf angle, α ,
- decrease slightly as doubler overlap increases, and
- decrease with increasing damage length for $\alpha = 12^\circ$ while no trend is clear for $\alpha = 6^\circ$.

The absence of distinct trends in stresses for $\alpha = 6^\circ$ may be caused by the large scarf adhesive area. For smaller angles the length of the scarf joint, and hence its area, increases. A large joint area distributes local stress peaks so that trends from varying the geometry could be lost in small numerical variations in the finite element analysis.

Doubler adhesive tensile and shear stresses follow the same trends as the scarf adhesive stresses except that they decrease as scarf angle increases. This implies that there is an optimum scarf angle which depends on the ultimate stresses of the adhesive. At the optimum angle the scarf adhesive and doubler adhesive will fail simultaneously. If the stresses are assumed to vary linearly with scarf angles between 6° and 12° the optimum scarf angle may be determined from the data developed. Figure 5 shows the variation of scarf and doubler adhesive stresses versus scarf angle for a repair with a 2.5 mm damage length and 40 mm doubler overlap (since scarf and doubler stresses are slightly lower for the longer doubler).

Fig. 5 - Adhesive stresses versus scarf angle.

For failure governed by maximum shear stress theory the optimum scarf angle is around 5°. For failure governed by maximum stress theory the optimum scarf angle is around 7°. Because the doubler adhesive stresses are less sensitive than scarf adhesive stresses to scarf angle changes it is more desirable that the scarf angle be too small rather than too large.

Adhesive inelasticity will also influence the optimum scarf angle. The rapid increase of scarf adhesive stresses with scarf angle suggests that some minimum scarf angle may still be optimal even with highly inelastic adhesives. The addition of a doubler may not increase the ultimate strength of the repair. The stresses at the end of the doubler adhesive layer and at the lower surface of the scarf adhesive layer may be higher than the stresses in the joint without a doubler. For example the doubler on the 6° scarf joint lowers the stresses in the scarf adhesive but the tensile stresses in the doubler adhesive are higher than the tensile stresses in the joint without the doubler.

For the 12° scarf joint the doubler lowers shear stress in the joint but raises tensile stresses slightly. Improvement here depends on which strength criterion governs failure. The scarf adhesive tensile stress increases because bending of the repair more than offsets the reduction in load due to the doubler. For larger scarf angles the section stiffness of the joint decreases and this bending effect may be more pronounced.

The higher stresses in the tapered edge of the original composite laminate compared to the tapered edge of the replacement composite are also caused by bending. The edge of the original composite laminate is at an outer surface in a region of pronounced bending while the edge of the replacement composite is inside the joint in a region of much lower bending.

Experimental data reported by G. Lubin et al. for boron/epoxy scarf joints follow the trends predicted here for graphite/epoxy (5). The change in failure stress between $\alpha = 6^\circ$ and $\alpha = 9^\circ$ for a scarf joint between boron/epoxy and titanium is very close to that predicted based on the finite element analysis of scarf joints between graphite/epoxy adherends. Also failure load for a 6° scarf joint with a feathered edge steel doubler does increase as doubler length increases although experimental scatter is large.

A finite element analysis with a much finer mesh at the ends of the adhesive layer gave a peak value of maximum shear stress equal to that for the coarse mesh shown in Figure 3. However, the stress peaks were narrower and the stress values in the middle of the joint were much lower. This indicates that the adhesive stresses are quite concentrated at the ends of the adhesive layer and suggests that the uniform shear stress typically assumed in this type of joint is very misleading.

Conclusions

The results of this study may be summarized as follows:

- Finite element studies indicate stress peaks at the ends of scarf joints which may be very important in determining joint strength.
- Maximum stresses in other parts of the joint occur at the tips of the tapered edges of the replacement material and the original laminate and in the doubler directly over the tip of the replacement material.
- The optimal scarf angle for the repair studied is around 5° for adhesive shear failure and around 7° for adhesive tensile failure.

- Increasing doubler length lowers adhesive stresses slightly.
- Addition of a doubler may not increase joint strength because of the bending effects induced.
- Bending of a repair with an adhesive scarf joint and a doubler may be modeled by treating each section of the specimen as a layered beam.

Nomenclature

E_1	lamina elastic modulus in filament direction
E_2	lamina elastic modulus in transverse direction
E_3	lamina elastic modulus in thickness direction
ν_{12}	lamina major Poisson's ratio
ν_{matrix}	Poisson's ratio of composite matrix
G_{12}	lamina inplane shear modulus
E_x	laminate elastic modulus in the x-direction
ν_{yz}	laminate Poisson's ratio for y-z-plane
G_{yz}	laminate shear modulus in y-z-plane
P	applied load
z	specimen deflection
e	eccentricity of the applied load
(EI)	effective section modulus
E_n	elastic modulus of the n^{th} layer
I_n	moment of inertia of the n^{th} layer about the neutral axis
N	the number of layers

References

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